

Water for the city and its development

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Citizens' complaints about the absence of drinking water services have been a constant feature in the local media over the last year. Information on cuts, awareness campaigns and transparency in compensation measures, such as tanker routes, are requested.

At a time of generative artificial intelligence, when internet connectivity is being debated as an emerging basic service, the deficiency in water supply and treatment continues to condition the lives of the people of Loja.

Adding up the damage to the families, the inconclusive tasks and the prices that have to be paid to obtain water tanks, it could be argued that a major public investment, supported by all the inhabitants of the canton, to renovate the water supply system, is both convenient and profitable.

However, no public spaces for communication, participation and debate are proposed to establish minimum agreements, contributions and commitments from the parties involved to solve this difficulty.

There are many channels of information, but not of dialogue. Communication is a two-way street; it is consensus based on knowing and understanding the points of view of the interlocutors. Messages on social networks, radio broadcasts, press releases in newspapers or bulletins from public relations offices are inputs to build a dialogue that someone must lead. The city council is expected to take the lead in guiding citizen voices, but neighbours or neighbourhood presidents can also take the lead. Delaying conversations to design an intervention plan will only delay progress and opportunities for well-being.